

Factors Affecting the Success of Computer Based Student Attendance System: Student Perspective in the Selected University in Sri Lanka

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Introduction

Background of the Study

Recording attendance of participants for an event, activity or job has a long history and continuing in many sectors including education due to its importance for the decision making. Attendance systems were first introduced in 1888 to track employee entry and exit times in factories, but today they play a crucial role in various fields, especially education. The conventional paper-based manual attendance system in universities is time-consuming and prone to errors (Dassanayake & Wanniarachchi, 2020), as it allows students to place forged signatures impersonating others and relies on human verification. To address these issues, various cutting-edge technologies have been proposed in university level in various places nationally and internationally, including Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, Biometric systems, GPS systems, facial recognition, barcode-based systems, and QR code-based systems (Dassanayake & Wanniarachchi, 2020).

Computer-based information systems developed using those technologies identified as important for efficient student information management in higher education institutions (Ahmad et al., 2019). The information systems that are used for attendance taking with those technologies in different contexts reported varying levels of efficacy or efficiency. It's possible that certain computer-based attendance systems have enhanced the maintenance of student attendance records by streamlining the process, lowering errors, and providing accurate data for analysis (Mijić et al., 2019). Even so, such

implementations reported to have faced difficulties like technological problems, user resistance, or partial acceptance, which would have led to less noticeable gains or perhaps the inability to achieve the desired goals (Sudha, K. L., et al., 2015). The success of computer-based students attendance information system defines as a system that meet the demands of the institution while managing attendance data accurately and effectively through precise work flows to decrease human resource requirements and cost (Ali, N.S. et al. ,2022). It depends on things like information quality, which guarantees accurate data for making decisions; system quality, which guarantees a solid and user-friendly platform; service quality, which offers efficient support and communication; user training, which gives users the tools they need to use the system efficiently; user attitudes, which promote engagement and adoption; and privacy and security measures, which protect data integrity and comply with regulations (Ali, N.S. et al. ,2022; Santos, A.B.G. et al. ,2021;, Helwani, S. and Zuanuwar, M. ,2020). All of these socio-technical elements work together to create a system that guarantees user happiness, promotes informed decision-making, and improves administrative efficiency in the context of state universities in Sri Lank is required for the success of such system.

Problem Statement

Though the computer-based students attendance systems are developed and use in various higher education institutes in Sri Lanka, the success of those systems not always guaranteed (Dassanayake& Wanniarachchi, 2020). According to Laudon and Laudon (2015), the effectiveness and the success of an information system is a combination of technology, management, and organizational aspects. When technology, managerial, and organisational elements are harmoniously combined, information systems are successful and effective. Technology comprises the apparatus and framework that underpin the system, whilst management takes care of the oversight and upkeep of its functioning. Organisational factors take into account how the system fits within the organization's workflows and culture while also

supporting its objectives (Kenneth., et al (2016). When taken as a whole, these components guarantee that the system not only runs well but also makes a significant contribution to the goals of the company, adding value and encouraging expansion. Computer-based student attendance systems frequently fail to produce the desired results, despite their best efforts to increase productivity, accuracy, and administrative procedures. Enhanced record accuracy, more efficient attendance tracking, and more student involvement are some of these results. Failures may occur even when the technical criteria are met because of insufficient user training, reluctance to change, or subpar system integration. In addition, misalignments with the culture and aims of the organization may make implementation difficult (Kenneth., et al (2016). In order to guarantee that these systems achieve their goals and make a meaningful contribution to institutional effectiveness and educational results, it is imperative that these problems be addressed. Many of the previous research has largely focused on technical aspects, neglecting the critical social and organizational dimensions of information systems (Maqableh, M., et al., 2021). However, the existing literature does not provide adequate information related to the student perspective of the success of computer-based students attendance system in the state university context in Sri Lanka considering technological, organizational and management dimensions.

Research objectives

The main aim of this study is to investigate the factors affecting the success of the computer-based student attendance system. Therefore, the main objectives of this study are to:

1. Identify the socio-technical factors that affect the success of the computer-based student attendance system.
2. Identify the affect of the above identified factors on the success of the computer-based student attendance system.

Methodology

This study followed a mixed approach as it conducted systematic literature review to identify factors influencing the success of computer-based student attendance system and questionnaire survey to test the conceptual model developed using the identified factors from the socio-technical perspective (Shaanika, 2022). A conceptual model (Figure 1) was developed to examine the factors affecting the success of the computer-based student attendance system from the students' perspective. This conceptual model was preliminarily developed based on the factors identified through the literature review under the theoretical underpinning of McLean's Information Systems Success Model and Seddon's Model of Information Systems Success the frameworks commonly used to assess the effectiveness and success of information systems within organizations. (Hussein et al., 2007; Sabherwal et al., 2006). Consequently, six (06) hypotheses were developed to test the model.

Though there are many stake holders of student attendance system, undergraduate was identified as the unit of analysis since they are directly connected to the process (Hassan & Zubair Asghar, 2016; Mishra et al., 2021, Dassanayake & Wanniarachchi, 2020.; Hassan & Zubair Asghar, 2016; Wei Lun et al., 2019). Therefore, the undergraduates in state universities in Sri Lanka were identified as the population of our study. Accordingly, 200 undergraduates of the selected state university were invited randomly for an online questionnaire survey considering the convenience of data collection. The questionnaire comprised of two sections, one is to collect demographic information of respondents and the other is with 5-point Likert-scale questions measuring constructs in the conceptual model. The data were analyzed with the support of SmartPLS (version 3.0) statistical software.

Analysis and Findings

A sample of 150 responses were gathered from the data collection. From the collected sample, 21 responses were excluded after considering the missing values and unintentional responses. The sample dataset was checked and confirmed for validity and reliability.

Demographic Information of the sample analysis

Gender Distribution was 64.6 % and 35.4 % respectively for Male and Female. After data cleansing, 73 samples from Male and 40 Samples from Female were valid.

Undergraduates from a state university in Sri Lanka made up the study's sample. According to the demographic data analysis, most of the respondents were from the University of Sri Jayewardenepura representing 62.80% whereas the least number of respondents were from Southeastern University, university of Ruhuna and Sabaragamuwa University Management.

The analysis of responses relevant to construct measurements showed that the mean value for each construct is in the range of 3 to 5 and the standard deviations are between 0.75 and 0.9. This denotes that the majority of the respondents were on positive belief related to the constructs in the model. The model was tested using multiple linear regression analysis. Prior to the analysis the dataset was tested to confirm its suitability for the multiple linear regression by checking a few assumptions. Firstly, confirmed the normal distribution of the factors. Secondly, confirmed the linear relationship between linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Thirdly, confirmed the values of the residuals were independent and correlated to each other in positive direction though the Durbin-Watson statistic (1.932). Fourthly, the variances of the residuals were checked for consistency and confirmed. Finally, confirmed the values of the residuals are normally distributed.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.839 ^a	0.703	0.686	0.37377	1.932

The model explained 70.3% (R² 0.703) of success of computer-based student attendance system. It describes the combination of information quality, system quality, service quality, user training, user attitudes, privacy, and security with the ability to describe 70.3% of success of computer-based Student attendance system based on the sample selected

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient -Beta Value	t value	Sig.	Result
H1: IQ-> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.118	1.467	0.145	Rejected

H2: SQ-> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.147	1.678	0.096	Rejected
H3: SV-> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.124	1.659	0.1	Rejected
H4: UA-> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.426	5.156 **	0	Accepted
H5: UT -> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.025	0.29	0.773	Rejected
H6: PS -> Success of Computer-based SAS	0.169	2.256 *	0.026	Accepted

Note: *- P<0.05 ** - P<0.001

H1 postulated that Information quality has a positive effect on Success of Computer-based SAS. However, due to the non-significance of Information quality ($\beta= 0.118$, $p= 0.145$), H1 was not supported. H2 claimed that the Success of Computer-based SAS is positively impacted by system quality. Due to non-significance of System quality ($\beta= 0.147$, $p= 0.096$), H2 was also not supported. H3 revealed that Service Quality ($\beta= 0.124$, $p= 0.1$) is not statistically significant and has a positive effect on Intention to Success of Computer-based SAS. User attitude towards student attendance system ($\beta= 0.426$, $p= 0.000$) is found as statistically significant and has a positive effect on Success of Computer-based SAS, supporting H4. Furthermore, User Training ($\beta= 0.025$, $p= 0.773$) is found statistically not significant and to have a positive effect on Success of Computer-based SAS, supporting H5. Moreover, H6 was supported due to the statistical significance of privacy and security ($\beta= 0.169$, $p= 0.026$). It also revealed that privacy and security have a positive effect on Success of Computer-based SAS.

Conclusion

The study aims to identify the social and technological factors that impact the success of these systems, which can contribute to the existing literature on designing and implementing information systems. The findings of this

study could potentially provide insights into the development of theoretical frameworks and models that can better explain the socio-technical perspective of implementing information systems, particularly in the context of student attendance systems.

The key contribution lies in the identification of socio-technical factors that significantly impact the success of computer-based student attendance systems. Through a literature review, the study developed a conceptual model based on established theoretical frameworks. The questionnaire survey conducted among undergraduates testing the conceptual model constructs. The findings highlight the pivotal role of user attitudes, privacy, and security in influencing the success of computer-based student attendance systems, emphasizing the significance of user-centric design and data protection measures. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of considering information quality, system quality, service quality, and user training in the design and implementation of such systems. Furthermore, the study's rigorous methodological approach, including data collection from undergraduates in state universities in Sri Lanka, enhances the credibility and generalizability of the findings. By addressing the existing gap in literature regarding the socio-technical dimensions of computer-based student attendance systems, this study contributes valuable insights that can inform future research and practice in designing and implementing information systems in educational contexts. In conclusion, this study enriches the understanding of the factors influencing the success of computer-based student attendance systems, providing a foundation for developing theoretical frameworks and models that better capture the socio-technical perspective of information system implementation in higher education institutions.

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